

Impact of Novel Techniques of Smart Drugs Delivery System for Cancer Treatment and its Challenges

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Abstract:- “A smart drug delivery system consists of intelligent nanocarriers, process selection, and relaxation techniques. This study highlights the recent novel development of Smart Drug Delivery Systems for a variety of technical nanocarriers, including liposomes, micelles, dendrimers, mesoporous silica nanoparticles, gold nanoparticles, super paramagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes, and quantum dots and their impact on cancer treatments. This study is expected to be of widespread interest to those who are looking for new future research in this field and to those who are about to start their research into smart nano-carrier-based drug delivery. Smart Drug Delivery Systems could distribute drugs to low-dose sites and regulate means to remove the side effects that are otherwise induced by traditional drug delivery systems. Chemotherapy is widely used for treating cancer, which would be the world's second-largest cause of death.” Choosing the best strategies for cancer cell detection follows the selection of an acceptable kind of nanocarrier. SDDs identify cancer sites by using the physiochemical variations between cancer cells and healthy cells. The location of the cancer cells is described precisely by two main methods: passive targeting and active targeting. Passive targeting allows for the cancer site to be recognized implicitly by using the Enhanced Permeability (EPR) effect. Active targeting uses cancer cell surface receptors which are over expressed specifically for targeting cancer cells. The next move is to discharge drugs at a particular concentration at the stated site. Drugs can be released by external or internal stimulation from nanocarriers, depending on the shape and smartness of nano-carriers.

Keywords:- Novel techniques, smart drugs delivery system (SDDS), cancer, treatment, challenges.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is the world's second-largest cause of death. “It is responsible for reported deaths of 9.6 million in 2018. About 1 in 6 deaths worldwide are due to cancer. Around 70 percent of cancer deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries such as India^[1, 2]. Chemotherapy^[3, 4] plays a vital role in the treatment of the micro-foci on undetectable cancer and free cancer cells. Chemotherapy chemicals destroy or block cancer cell growth^[5]. As cancer cells evolve faster than healthy organisms, the key targets of chemotherapeutic agents are fast-growing cells; and as there are healthier cells that still grow rapidly, chemotherapy drugs often destroy such fast-growing healthy cells. This needless attack causes a malfunction in traditional chemotherapy^[6]. Moreover, multidrug resistance (MDR)^[7-9] provides another big impediment to effective chemotherapy. By developing cytotoxic drug tolerance during or shortly after therapy, MDR helps cancer cells avoid the chemotherapeutic impact. Conventional chemotherapy drawbacks have led to the development of advanced Nano carrier-based drug delivery schemes, also known as the Advanced Drug Delivery System (SDDS). SDDSs consent to prescribe medications to particular targeted sites^[10]. While Paul Ehrlich's magic bullet concept^[11] is the cornerstone of the connection between drug delivery and nanoparticles, Speiser et al.^[12] first reported well-controlled active delivery using a bead polymerization technique.

The SDDS are the basis for Nano carriers. Unfortunately, not all kinds of Nano carriers are effective as drug carriers in SDDSs. In order to qualify as an ideal Nano carrier in SDDSs, a Nano carrier should meet certain basic criteria, addressed in detail in the related sections. This analysis highlights the most known Nano carriers: Liposomes, micelles, dendrimers, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs), gold nanoparticles (GNPs), super-paramagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs), carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and quantum dots (QDs) in their structure, classification, synthesis, and smartness. Choosing the best cancer cell detection strategies follows the selection of a suitable kind of Nano carrier. SDDS uses the physiochemical differences between cancer cells and healthy cells in order to recognize cancer sites. The cancer cell site is precisely defined by two main methods: passive targeting and active targeting. Passive targeting enables an implied detection of the cancer site by the use of the Enhanced Permeability (EPR) effect^[13]. The direct response uses surface receptors of cancer cells that are expressed on

the surface to specifically target cancer cells like a guided missile ^[14]. The next step is to release drugs at the specified location at a specific concentration. Medicines may have been released from either the Nano carriers by external or internal stimulation, depending on the form of Nano carriers and their intelligence ^[15].

This study concentrates on three different forms of DDS nanoparticles reflecting different sources of nanoparticles materials: nanoparticles (MSNs), gold nanoparticles (GNPs), super-paramagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs), carbon nanotubes (CNTs). They integrate the methods and applications in providing smart drugs for effects on cancer care. The study also outlines the current barriers that nanoparticles could face for clinical use, and the future development of DDS nanoparticles.

II. SCOPE AND CHALLENGES

SDDS reflects no exception. The obstacles to efficient SDDSs are the toxicity of the Nano carriers of the human body, cost-effectiveness of the system, diversity and heterogeneity in cancer, and lack of clear regulatory guidance. Nano carriers carry and activate the anticancer drugs at the targeted sites to destroy the cancer cell. The concern is with the ultimate fate of drug-carrying Nano carriers. Traditional Nano carriers accumulate in different vital organs such as the lungs, spleen, kidneys, liver, and heart, depending on the chemical composition, size, form, specific surface area, surface charge, and the presence and absence of a shell around the Nano carrier. In animal cases, several in vitro and in vivo toxicity tests have been carried out; toxicity studies in the human body are, unfortunately, very limited. There is a large area available for toxicity research. In the transformation of CNTs into the best bioactive management modules, there are great challenges, including purification and dispersibility. Taking into account their positive characteristics such as biocompatibility, non-immunogenicity, stability, and easy modification, they appear to be very promising as drug delivery systems. However, limitations, such as the surface / mass ratio, non-biodegradability, and purification, pose challenges. In conclusion, before fully exploiting the potential of the CNT, it is imperative to generate data on their safety, effectiveness, and profitability.

III. IMPACT OF NOVEL TECHNIQUES OF SMART DRUGS DELIVERY SYSTEM

The drug delivery system (DDS) was clinically and preclinically used to distribute medicinal substances for the treatment of diseases. Conventional DDS is either given orally or by injection. Notwithstanding many benefits of traditional DDS, such as ease of administration and widespread acceptance by patients. A smart drug delivery system utilizing liposomes as Nano carriers consist of smart Nano carriers carrying anti-cancer drugs to the cancer site, cancer site location mechanisms, and pre-located cancer site stimulation techniques. The following sections analyze eight

Nano carriers in detail, their targeting mechanisms, and stimulus techniques.

Smart Nano carrier particles in the order of 1–100 nm are popularly known as nanoparticles, with at least one dimension. Currently, nanoparticles are graded as Variable Surface Volume (VSSA). Nanoparticles are generally defined as particles with a volume of VSSA equal to or greater than 60 m² / cm³ of the material ^[16]. If nanoparticles are used as transport tubes for other compounds, they'll be called Nano carriers. Conventional Nano carriers do not have the ability to retain and release drugs at the right concentration on the target site, under external or internal strain. Therefore archetypal Nano carriers aren't smart. They have to be changed or functionalized to make them smart. Smart Nano carriers should have the following characteristics. Second, smart Nano carriers can prevent surgery from cleaning up the body's immune system. Second, they can accumulate only at the target site. Thirdly, smart Nano carrier will release the cargo at the targeted site at the correct concentration under external or internal stimulation. Finally, chemotherapeutics and other items should be co-delivered, such as genetic materials, imaging agents, etc. ^[17–19].

There are several steps to turn traditional Nano carriers into intelligent ones, depending on the Nano carriers types and applications (Table .1). Second, Nano carriers face many biological barriers including the reticuloendothelial system (RES) cleaning up on the way to the intended location. The RES briefly takes the Nano carrier out of circulation and accumulates in the liver, spleen, or bone marrow some Nano carriers carrying anti-cancer drugs. PEGylation is a special way of finishing the washing process. PEGylation lets Nano carriers escape RES. First described on PEGylation, by Davies and Abuchowsky^[20]. Unfortunately, PEGylation greatly decreases cell intake of medicinal products ^[21, 22]. This twist is known as the PEGylation dilemma ^[23, 24]. Second, Nano carriers can be functionalized to distinguish the cancer cells precisely out of healthy ones. The physiochemical variations between cancer cells and healthy ones are the distinguishing marks that distinguish the two types of cells. The surface of the cancer cells overexpresses a few proteins. The main destinations of the smart Nano carrier are the over-expressed proteins. The Nano carriers are modified with ligands to balance the overexpressed proteins. The smart Nano carrier's ligands identify the receptor proteins into cells. Thirdly, delivering the drug to the destination site is not the end of the process. The next big challenge is to free up the drug under pressure from the smart bag. To make Nano carriers sensitive to the stimulus system, different chemical groups may be grafted on the surface of the Nano carriers. Fourth, it also modifies the codelivery of anti-cancer drugs along with other substances, including genetic materials ^[25], imaging agents, or even additional anti-cancer drugs. Liposomes, micelles, dendrimers, GNPs, quantum dots, and MSNs show co-delivery promise ^[26–30]. Eight promising Nano carriers are discussed in detail below concerning their structure, classification, synthesis, and smartness (Table.1).

Subject	Novel Techniques/Research Gap	Future Recommendation
Smart nanocarriers	PEGylation[20]. This having some research gap either than liposome.	PEGylation greatly decreases cell intake of medicinal products[21,22] Various studies indicate the possibility of stopping the cancer-causing by PEGylation
Liposome and its smartness	large uni-lamellar (LUV) vesicles and small uni-lamellar (SUV) vesicles[33,34]. This having some research gap either than Micelles	Liposome to target the cancer site specifically. Several studies indicate the possibility of stopping the cancer-causing by liposome
Micelles and its smartness	PG-PCL, PEEP-PCL[64], PEG-PCL[65] and PEG-DSPE[66]. This having some research gap either than Dendrimers	The co-delivery technique, using a multifunctional micelle, is very important for the synergetic effects in cancer treatment. Several studies indicate the possibility of stopping the cancer-causing by Micelles
Dendrimers and its smartness	nucleus, dendron-branching, and surface-active groups[75], poly (PPI or POPAM), PAMAM, POPAM, POMAM[78], polylysine dendrimer, dendritic hydrocarbon, dendrimer based on carbon / oxygen, dendrimer based on porphyrin, ionic dendrimer, silicon based dendrimer, dendrimer based on phosphorus[79], and Newkome dendrimer[80]. This having some research gap either than mesoporous silica	The cationic nature of PAMAM, among other dendrimers, makes this extremely useful for the transmission of genetic materials. Many studies indicate the possibility of stopping the cancer-causing by Dendrimers
Nanoparticles from mesoporous silica and its smartness	porous silica (SiO ₂), mixtures of zeolite-silica gel with a well-defined and uniform porosity[96] Usually there are two types of MSNs, namely (1) ordered hollow or rattle-like meso-porous silica NPs (MCM-41, MCM-48, and SBA-15), and (2) meso-porous silica NPs[102]. This having some research gap either than Gold nanocarriers	Its controlled drug delivery capacity. So many studies indicate the possibility of stopping the cancer-causing by various kind of nanoparticles from mesoporous silica.
Gold nanocarriers and its smartness	GNPs [113] are metal nanocarriers that come in special shapes and sizes. GNPs have excellent prospects as metallic candidates to carry payloads. This having some research gap either than SPIONs	Various ligands can change the surface of GNPs for targeted delivery of drugs. Various studies indicate the possibility of silencing the cancer-causing gene by transfection of GNP
Super paramagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) and its smartness	The SPIONs group also includes mixed iron oxides, such as copper, cobalt, and nickel. As magnetic particles are reduced to 10–20 nm they show a strange phenomenon called super para-magnetism [130,131]. This having some research gap either than CNTs	SPION synthesis methods are distinct, including co-precipitation processes, thermal decomposition, hydrothermal, micro-emulsion, sono-chemical, microwave-assisted synthesis. Some studies indicate the possibility of stopping the cancer-causing by SPIONs
Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and its smartness	There are two types of CNTs: single walled (SWCNT) and multi-walled (MWCNT) [141,142]. This having some research gap either than QDs	Functionalized CNTs can be used as early cancer diagnostic instruments [153]. Many studies indicate the possibility of stopping the cancer-causing by CNTs
Quantum dots (QDs) and their smartness	QD-based SDDSs had drawn significant attention for a variety of reasons. QD's have a tiny core diameter of 2–10 nm. This having some research gap either than current new possibilities.	QDs are especially common for cancer imaging, due to their inherent fluorescence. Some studies indicate the possibility of stopping the cancer-causing by Quantum dots

Table 1: Novel techniques of smart drugs delivery system have played more important role for the cancer treatment

A. LIPOSOME AND ITS SMARTNESS

Liposomes [31], based on phospholipids are naturally occurring amphipathic nanocarriers. Phospholipids, an essential part of the cell membrane, consist of a hydrophobic fatty acid tail and a phosphate-dependent hydrophilic head. Gregory Gregordians demonstrated in 1973 that when phospholipids are introduced into an aqueous medium, they self-assemble into a two-layer vesicle with the non-polar

ends forming a bilayer, and the polar ends facing the water. The center of the bilayer will pull water or water-soluble medicines [32] in. Depending on the number of bilayers and the size of the liposome, there are two forms: multi-lamellar vesicles and uni-lamellar vesicles. It is possible to divide uni-lamellar vesicles further into two groups: large uni-lamellar (LUV) vesicles and small uni-lamellar (SUV) vesicles [33, 34]. Many methods for preparing liposomes [35, 36] are available,

including the thin film hydration process or the Bangham method^[37], reverse phase evaporation^[38], solvent injection technique^[39], and detergent dialysis^[40]. Many failures are linked to conventional methods. To overcome these constraints, some revolutionary technologies such as supercritical fluid technology, a supercritical anti-solvent method^[41], and supercritical reverse-phase evaporation^[42] have been built.

Conventional liposomes have many problems, including instability, insufficient preparation of drugs, the quicker release of drugs, and shorter circulation times in the blood, so they are not wise. Conventional liposomal functionality^[44], makes them intelligent. Like other nanocarriers, liposomes need to resolve the RES issue, too. PEGylation allows the liposomes to escape RES. PEGylated liposomes, therefore, have a longer circulating time in the blood^[45]. Smart nanocarriers can compute the difference between healthy cells and cancerous ones. Monoclonal antibodies, antibody fragments, proteins, peptides, vitamins, carbohydrates, and glycoproteins are usually grafted onto the liposome to target the cancer site specifically^[46-49]. Smart liposomes are responsive to various external and internal stimulants including changes in pH, transformation of enzymes, redox reactions, light, ultrasound, and microwaves^[50-52]. A radio-ligand-functionalized liposome is recognized as a liposome marked with radiation. Radiolabeled liposomes^[53] can be used to determine the biodistribution of liposomes in the body and to diagnose the tumor in accordance with treatment. Theranostic liposomes^[55, 56] are classified as liposomes that can contain both therapeutic agents as well as imagery^[54]. In addition to providing imaging agents along with chemotherapy, liposomes are promising in the co-delivery of two chemotherapeutic drugs, chemotherapeutic gene agents^[57] and chemotherapeutic anticancer drugs^[58].

B. MICELLES AND ITS SMARTNESS

Having both hydrophilic and hydrophobic elements, amphiphilic molecules show peculiar self-assembly characteristics when exposed to a solvent. If the solvent is hydrophilic and its concentration reaches the critical concentration of the micelle (CMC), the polar parts of the co-polymer are drawn toward the solvent, while the hydrophobic parts are oriented away from the solvent. The hydrophobic portions thus form a nucleus, whereas the hydrophilic portions form a crown. This type of arrangement is called a polymeric micellar direct or regular^[59, 60]. Amphiphilic molecules exposed to a hydrophobic solvent on the other hand build a reverse structure known as a reverse micelle. That is, in a reverse micelle, the hydrophilic portions make the heart and the hydrophobic portions make the corona^[61-63]. Examples of some micelles are PG-PCL, PEEP-PCL^[64], PEG-PCL^[65], and PEG-DSPE^[66].

The processing of micelles is based on the copolymer solubility used^[67]. Two processes are used for a relatively water-soluble co-polymer, namely the direct dissolution method and the casting process for films. By contrast, dialysis or oil is used in water treatment because the co-polymer is not readily water-soluble^[68, 69]. By crossing the CMC, Micelles can experience the immature release of the

drugs. In addition, animals blood contact and plasma protein absorption can disrupt the micelle-blood balance. The solution to that problem is a smart micellar. Usually, micelles are cross-linked to overcome the aforementioned problems; that is, they bind two polymer chains by forming disulfides^[70]. There are two types of cross-linking schemes: core cross-linking polymer micelles, and cross-linking polymer micelles. Various types of ligands are used to actively target cancer cells to decorate the micellar surface, including folic acid, peptides, carbohydrates, antibodies, aptamers, and so on^[66]. The micelle's heart or corona may be functionalized at the right concentration to activate the anti-cancer drug. In micellar SDDSs, the stimuli used are pH gradients, temperature changes, ultrasound^[71], enzymes, and oxidation^[66]. The co-delivery technique, using a multifunctional micelle, is very important for the synergetic effects in cancer treatment. Seo et al. have reported a method of co-delivery based on the temperature-responsive micelle, which can hold genes together with anti-cancer drugs^[72]. In cancer detection and monitoring, single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), and ultrasonography all play an important role. The surface of the micelle can be drawn with an imager^[73]. Kennedy and colleagues reported combined doxorubicin delivery with ultrasound imaging of tumors^[74].

C. DENDRIMERS AND THEIR SMARTNESS

Polymers with several branches are called dendrimers and can be represented as a suction cup graphically. There are three distinct sections of Dendrimer: nucleus, dendron-branching, and surface-active groups^[75]. The dendrimer's physiochemical properties are calculated on the dendrimer surface by the active groupings. Depending on the surface groups this can be either hydrophobic or hydrophilic. Because of its nanoscale size, its monodispersity^[76], water-solubility, bio-compatibility, and highly branched structure, it is of great interest. Because of the size of the nanoscale, it growing to be used as a drug carrier^[77]. The branched structure makes polyvalent the dendrimer. Moreover, all its active surface groups face outwards, resulting in a greater degree of encapsulation of the compound. Different forms of dendrimer have been reported, such as poly (PPI or POPAM), PAMAM, POPAM, POMAM^[78], polylysinedendrimer, dendritic hydrocarbon, dendrimer based on carbon/oxygen, dendrimer based on porphyrin, ionic dendrimer, silicon-based dendrimer, dendrimer based on phosphorus^[79], and Newcomedendrimer^[80]. Dendrimer model approaches which are commonly known include the divergent method^[81] and the convergent method^[82], respectively. Fritz Vogtle et al. in 1978 first introduced to Dendrimers^[83]. The poly (amidoamine) of Tomalia (PAMAM)^[84, 85] and the 'arboreal system' of Newcome^[86,87] are the dendritic structures that have been extensively investigated and gained widespread attention.

Conventional dendrimers face rapid clearance of the immune system and lower absorption of cells from cancer. Adjustment to dendrimer is the solution to those limitations. Chemical modification, linear polymer copolymerization,

and hybridization with other nanocarriers, as mentioned to date^[89], are options to overcome those limitations. Peptides, proteins, carbohydrates, aptamers, antibodies, etc. may modify the surface of dendritic structures to actively target the cancer site. For different stimulus-responsive systems such as light, heat, pH transfer, protein, and enzyme transformation, the dendrimer surface can also be changed^[90, 91]. The cationic nature of PAMAM, among other dendrimers, makes this extremely useful for the transmission of genetic materials. Efficiency in distribution is a function of producing PAMAM. In 1993 Haensler and Szoka were the first to announce the availability of PAMAM based nucleic acid^[75, 92]. A very promising tumor-imaging dendritic contrast agent^[93].

D. NANOPARTICLES FROM MESOPOROUS SILICA AND ITS SMARTNESS

Mesoporous materials are materials containing pores in diameters between 2 and 50 nm, as described by IUPAC^[94]. MSNs^[95] have porous silica (SiO₂) structures similar to that of a rabbit. 40 years ago, the term MSN was coined to describe mixtures of zeolite-silica gel with a well-defined and uniform porosity^[96]. MSNs are widely studied because of their tunable particle size (50 nm to 300 nm), uniform and adjustable pore size (2–6 nm)^[97], large area, high pore volume, and biocompatibility^[98–100]. Tunable particle size is an important requirement for being a smart nanocarrier, and the size of the tunable pore allows the loading of drugs of different molecular types. The high surface areas of the inner (pores) and outer surface are suitable for grafting on MSNs of different functional classes. Besides biocompatibility, the adhesion of this carrier to cancer cells by the action of the EPR makes it a great choice for them^[101]. Usually, there are two types of MSNs, namely (1) ordered hollow or rattle-like mesoporous silica NPs (MCM-41, MCM-48, and SBA-15), and (2) mesoporous silica NPs^[102,104,105]. Among those MSNs, MCM-41, synthesized by a Mobil Corporation scientist, is the most researched MSN for Biomedical Applications. In 2001, MCM-41 became known for its controlled drug delivery capacity^[96]. Methods for generating MSNs are the soft template method and the hard template method [106-110].

E. GOLD NANOCARRIERS AND THEIR SMARTNESS

Due to their unique features such as customizable size, large surface-to-volume ratio, easy synthesis, noble optical properties, cancer cell thermal ablation, and quick surface functionalization, metallic nanocarriers are of considerable interest^[111]. Studies show that the size and shape of the colloidal nanocarriers depend on the intercellular take-up of nanocarriers^[112]. GNPs^[113] are metal nanocarriers that come in special shapes and sizes. GNPs have excellent prospects as metallic candidates to carry payloads. Payloads may be drug molecules or large bimolecular like proteins, DNA, and RNA. GNPs are also interesting because of the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) phenomenon^[114,115] which enables them to convert light to heat and disperse the heat produced to kill the cancer cells. GNPs are mainly synthesized by a variety of paths, including chemical^[116], physical^[117], and biological^[118,119]. The blood-brain barrier (BBB)^[120] could be greatly surmounted by greasing GNP surfaces with proper ligands. Smart nanocarriers should be

chemically stable in biological media, biocompatible, efficient in targeting, and sensitive to external or internal stimuli. Unmodified GNPs are unstable in blood and face a higher absorption of RES. To surmount these limits, gold nanocarriers need to be PEGylated. Under physiological conditions, PEGylated GNPs exhibit greater solubility and stability^[122]. Various ligands can change the surface of GNPs for the targeted delivery of drugs. For example, transferrin (TF) can be grafted to the surface of GNPs, because many tumors over-express the TF receptor on their surface^[123]. Even folic acid may alter the surface of GNP since folic acid receptors are often overexpressed on different tumor cells^[124,125]. The substance can be discharged from GNP by either (1) external stimuli (laser, ultrasound, and X-ray, light^[126] or (2) internal stimuli (pH, redox, metalloproteinase matrix)^[127]. Various studies indicate the possibility of silencing the cancer-causing gene by transfection of GNP^[128]. GNPs combined with fluorescently labeled heparin can be used to diagnose cancer sites^[129].

F. SUPERPARAMAGNETIC IRON OXIDE NANOPARTICLES (SPIONS) AND THEIR SMARTNESS

In 1960 Freeman et al. proposed the concept of using magnetic materials along with magnetic fields in medicine^[109]. The magnetic materials have the commonly studied SPIONs. Two SPIONs are small, synthetic maghemite and magnetite particles (Fe₃O₄) with cores ranging in diameter from 10 to 100 nm. The SPIONs group also includes mixed iron oxides, such as copper, cobalt, and nickel. As magnetic particles are reduced to 10–20 nm they show a strange phenomenon called super para-magnetism. When applying a magnetic field, the magnetic nanoparticles are magnetized to their saturation but do not have any residual magnetism after removing the magnetic field^[130,131]. Production of SPIONs includes three processes including a physical process, a wet chemistry process, and a microbial system^[132]. SPION synthesis methods are distinct, including co-precipitation processes, thermal decomposition, hydrothermal, micro-emulsion, sonochemical, microwave-assisted synthesis^[133]. Chemical synthesis is amongst others the most prevalent.

The functionality builds on the smartness of post-manufactured SPIONs. Functionalization prevents aggregation of SPIONs, protects their surfaces from oxidation, provides a barrier for drug conjugation and ligand targeting increases blood circulation by avoiding RES, and decreases non-specific targets^[130]. Stimulus-responsive polymer-coated SPIONs undergo intensive research for selective drug delivery. Responsive polymers undergo physical and chemical transformations including process, hydrophobicity, solubility, and conformation. A recent study has shown that polymer-modified SPIONs are dually sensitive to pH gradients and temperature changes^[135]. For regulating the carrier an external magnetic field can be used. Because of the existence of the phosphate group, nucleic acids are negatively charged; thus SPIONs can be modified to carry genetic materials with cationic lipids and polymers^[136]. SPIONs are members of the theranostic-property family of nanocarriers. This is observed by an external magnetic field as a magnetic nanocarrier^[137,138].

G. CARBON NANOTUBES (CNTS) AND THEIR SMARTNESS

The CNTs are a type of fullerene, a class of hollow spheres, ellipsoid, tubes, and several other types of allotropic carbon^[139,140]. The type is called the CNT when a sheet of graphene is rolled up into a smooth cylindrical tube. There are two types of CNTs: single-walled (SWCNT) and multi-walled (MWCNT)^[141,142]. The strong optical absorption of the CNT in the near-infrared region makes this particle a good candidate for photothermal ablation; however, nanoparticles with sizes ranging from 50 to 100 nm are easy to absorb. MWCNTs may cross the boundary between various cellular compartments, and PEGylated SWCNTs may be located in a specific cellular compartment. The CNTs can be synthesized by heating carbon black and graphite in a controlled flame environment. But this method cannot control the shape, scale, mechanical strength, consistency, and purity of the synthesized CNTs. Electric arc discharges^[142,143,144], the chemical vapor deposition method^[145,146,147], and the laser ablation method have been reported to address the limitations of the controlled flame collection. SWCNTs are more efficient in drug delivery than MWCNTs because of the better-defined SWCNT walls and comparatively more structural MWCNT defects^[5,144,148,149,150-153].

H. QUANTUM DOTS (QDS) AND THEIR SMARTNESS

Quantum dots^[154], semiconducting fluorescent nanocarriers, often consisting of hundreds to thousands of group II and group VI atoms and possessing unique photophysical properties^[155]. This nanocarrier may be used when releasing the drug at the desired position to image the tumor. The majority of commercially available QDs are made up of three components: a nucleus, a shell, and a cap. The center consists of a semiconductor material, e.g. CdSe. See. Another semiconductor, such as ZnS, is used to create shells that surround the semi-conductor center. A cap encapsulates the double layer QD's with various materials^[156]. QD-based SDDSs had drawn significant attention for a variety of reasons. QD's have a tiny core diameter of 2–10 nm. This role renders it useful as a tracer in other drug delivery systems. Second, versatile surface chemistry enables different approaches to modification of the surface of QD. Third, their photophysical properties provide extra QD mileage for real-time monitoring of drug-carrying and drug release^[157]. To synthesize QD's, either a top-down approach or a bottom-up process can be used. Molecular beam epitaxy (MBE)^[158], ion implantation, e-beam lithography, and x-ray lithography^[159] are part of top-down processing; on the other hand, colloidal QDs are prepared by self-assembly in chemical reduction solution, which is a bottom-up approach^[160]. As with other smart nanocarriers, the functionalization of archetypal QDs also plays an important role. As recorded for other nanocarriers, QDs also experience non-specific RES uptake. PEGylation is also a fantastic remedy for QDs. Properly PEGylated QDs can accumulate in tumor sites without a targeting ligand through an increased permeability and retention (EPR) effect. In order to effectively target a tumor site, various ligands such as peptides, folate, and large proteins (monoclonal antibodies) can be grafted onto the QD surface^[162]. Iannazzo and others. The promising prospects of controlled

drug delivery based on graphene QD have recently been demonstrated. They covalently attached QDs to the tumor-targeting module, biotin, to find the biotin receptor overexpressed on tumor cells. This process will successfully release a drug under pH stimulation^[163]. QDs are especially common for cancer imaging, due to their inherent fluorescence. A complex of folic acids has been used to diagnose ovarian cancer^[164]. Chemotherapeutic and siRNA co-delivery was developed to combat MDR^[165]. Gao et al. researched and optimized bioconjugated and polymer-encapsulated QD samples for cancer imaging^[166,167].

IV. MECHANISM OF CANCER TREATMENT AND IMPACT OF STIMULUS

When the anti-cancer drug-carrying intelligent nanocarrier passes the cleaning phase of our body's immune system, then the smart nanocarrier can find the cancerous area of the body. A smart drug delivery system uses two ways of focusing: passive targeting and active targeting^[168,169]. Passive targeting makes use of the EPR effect^[170] for the cancer site role. Successful targeting uses the ligand-receptor technique to locate the ultimate objective-the individual cancer cell.

A. Passive targeting

The penetration rate of drug-laden nanocarriers into a tumor is much higher than in normal tissue, due to the leaky endothelium of the tumor vasculature. This phenomenon is known as the enhanced permeability effect. The corporeal drainage system is the lymphatic channel. A defect in the lymphatic system contributes to nanoparticles deposited in the tumor. This retention is known as the enhanced retention effect. Both phenomena are collectively known as the EPR^[171] effect. Compared to healthy body tissue, the concentration of anti-cancer drugs in the tumor could be multiply increased by using this EPR effect. Another barrier to efficient accumulation of drug-laden nanocarriers in a solid tumor is interstitial fluid pressure (IFP)^[172,173] however; successful nanocarrier modifications can overcome many biological barriers, including IFP and RES^[174].

B. Active targeting

Active targeting means directing the nanocarriers that deliver the drug into cancer cells, such as guided missiles^[175]. Cancer cells and regular cells can be distinguished in terms of cell surface receptor expression and antigen production. Cell surface receptors are proteins found in the cell membrane that are responsible for trans-membrane communication. Cancer cells have various cell surface receptors usually recognized as cell markers such as folic acid and cell surface antigen suppression or overexpression. Drug-packed nanocarriers are equipped with targeting ligands. These ligands recognize their corresponding target on the surface of over-expressed cancer cells. Some ligands examined include folate, transferrin, anticorps, peptides, and aptamers.

C. The stimulus for drug release

Both kinds of stimuli are exogenous and are endogenous. An extra-corporeal signal is known as a temperature shift for the extraction of drugs from nanocarriers, such as a magnetic field, electromagnetic waves, an electric field, an exogenous stimulus. An endogenous stimulus is called a signal that is produced from within the body to release anti-cancer drugs. Examples of endogenous triggers include pH transition, the transformation of the enzymes, temperature, and redox reactions^[176].

D. Endogenous stimulus and its Impact

In the case of endogenous stimulation, the triggering signal comes from the internal pH level, the action of enzymes, and the action of body redox. Different forms of endogenous stimuli are discussed in more detail below^[177].

E. The pH-responsive stimulus

According to the Warburg effect, the tumor cells produce energy primarily via enhanced glycolysis, followed by lactic acid fermentation in the cytosol^[178]. This production of extra acids helps decrease the pH in cancer cells. The pH-responsive drug delivery mechanism is important because the pH level varies from organ to organ, and from tissue to tissue. In tumors, the extracellular pH has an acidic state compared to an intracellular pH much more stable^[179]. Thus pH has been described as an important physiological property for the delivery of smart drugs to tumor sites across several studies. This acidic extracellular pH is the result of poor blood flow, hypoxia, and lactic acid^[180] in tumors. The extracellular pH range approximately is 6–7^[181]. Apart from this pH gradient between cells, there is a pH change between cell compartments. The lysosomal pH is approximately 5 while the cytosol has a pH of 7.2^[182]. Usually, pH-sensitive nanocarriers store and stabilize anti-cancer drugs at physiological pH, then release the drug rapidly at a pH trigger stage; ensuring intracellular drug concentration reaches a peak. The goal can be accomplished by various methods including the introduction of ionizable chemical groups such as amines, phosphoric acid, and carboxyl groups, among others. These groups undergo pH-dependent physical and chemical changes that result in the release of drugs.

F. Redox sensitive stimulus

Glutathione sulphhydryl (GSH) has the greatest efficacy as an antioxidant. It contains 3 amino acids. GSH is present in higher concentrations in any mammalian tissue^[183]. GSH governs the reductive microenvironment. GSH concentration is at least four times higher in a tumor site than in normal cells. The intracellular concentration of GSH is 1000 times that of the bloodstream^[70,184]. GSH, a functional group with an R-S-S structure, will reduce the disulfide bonds of the nanocarriers. Disulfide bond reductions lead to the release of an encapsulated drug^[185] for instance, the GSH cell-site can reduce the disulfide bond of cross-linked micelles. Reducing disulfide bonds results in efficient unloading of nano-vehicle cargo^[186].

G. Enzyme stimulus

The nanocarriers of the enzyme-stimulus are called nanocarriers whose surfaces are modified to make the nanocarriers responsive to enzyme bio-catalytic action. Enzymes are catalysts for biochemical reactions which are produced by living organisms. Enzymes play a key role in regulating the functioning of cells; thus, they are very important targets for drug delivery. Enzymetriggered approaches use the enzyme that is overexpressed from the extracellular environment of tumor sites. This technique does not apply to the release of intracellular drugs, because intracellular enzyme concentrations in cancer cells and healthy cells are approximately the same^[187]. Proteases, an enzyme that breaks down proteins and peptides, are an ideal candidate for the extraction of liposomal drugs^[188,189].

H. Exogenous stimulus

In extrinsic stimulation systems, contrast agents have been used to imaging the accumulation of nanocarriers in cancer sites. An external factor such as a magnetic field, ultrasonic waves, light and electric fields^[190] stimulates the accumulated nanocarriers to release drugs at the correct concentration.

I. Magnetic field responsive stimulus

An extracorporeal magnetic field is used in magnetically induced systems after the injection of nanocarriers to store drug-charged nanocarriers in tumor sites. Some suitable candidates for magnetic stimulation are core-shell-shaped nanoparticles filled with silica, polymer, or magnetoliposome (liposome-encapsulated maghemitenanocrystals)^[191,192]. Magnete-guided nanocarriers may also carry genetic materials. The magnetic nanocarriers emit heat in the surrounding medium when positioned under an oscillating magnetic field. This heat brings with it structural changes in nanocarriers^[193–195].

J. Thermo-responsive stimulus

The drug-charged nanocarriers release their payloads in response to temperature changes in this process. At a predetermined temperature, the nanocarriers change their conformation, solubility, or hydrophilic and hydrophobic balance. A few nanocarriers release their cargo if they undergo a temperature change. The thermo-sensitive nanocarriers show a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) phenomenon^[196,197]. The aqueous polymer solutions show one phase below LCST and above-temperature phase separation. There is a systematic thermo-responsive analysis of micelles^[198, 199]. Thermo-sensitive hydrogels and poly (N-isopropyl acrylamide) (PNIPAAm) display sol-gel reactive temperature transitions^[200].

K. Light-triggered stimulus

The latest development of light-triggered drug delivery is a new path for the on-demand distribution of drugs. The light can be visible or near-infrared in the ranges of ultraviolet. The stimulation is accomplished by sensitizing the nanocarriers^[201–203] to the sun. CNTs and GNPs are good candidates for light stimulation, especially for the Near Infrared Range (NIR). Nanocarriers of metal absorb light and heat the absorbed light to kill cancer cells^[204].

L. Ultrasound-responsive stimulus

Ultrasound is under comprehensive investigation for the extraction of drugs from nanocarriers due to its non-invasive properties, deep body penetration, and non-ionizing irradiation^[205]. Using ultrasound can cause both mechanical and thermal effects to release the charged drug into the nanocarriers. Dromi et al.^[206] used high-intensity ultrasound-based waves to investigate the release of drugs from temperature-sensitive liposomes in 2007^[207 208].

M. Electric field-responsive stimulus

This stimulation approach uses an electrical field to switch on payloads. The aforementioned thermo-responsive, light-triggered, and ultrasonic stimulating systems also require large or specialized drug release equipment. On the contrary, electric fields can be easily manufactured and regulated^[209]. The conduction of polymers such as polypyrrole (PPy) is responsible for the electrical response stimulus. The nanocarriers are modified by conducting polymers, and the efficacy of conducting polymers depends on the choice of dopant and molecular weight of the medicine. Biotin is a dopant that has been tested experimentally^[210]. MWCNTs can be used as a conductive additive to boost electrical conductivity^[211]; however, hydrogels from polyelectrolytes are also considered^[212,213].

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, Cancer varies in severity and heterogeneity; that is, cancers still have undetermined types. Furthermore, the physical nature of cancer may vary from one person to another. Personalizing anti-cancer treatment is also a significant challenge. DNA /RNA-focused anti-cancer therapies have a promising future for making medicines safer and more personalized. The Drug Delivery System (DDS) based on nanoparticles is considered promising in treating cancer. Compared to conventional DDS, the DDS based on nanoparticles shows enhanced efficacy by increasing the half-life of vulnerable drugs and proteins; enhancing the solubility of hydrophobic drugs and allowing controlled and targeted release of drugs to diseased sites^[214]. Therefore the development of nanocarriers as carriers of DNA / RNA to destroy cancer cells can be a promising research field. The way traditional nanocarriers locate cancer cells, such as RES, rapid blood clearance (ABC), etc., faces several biological obstacles. Traditional nanocarriers are modified using different methods to resolve these barriers, including PEGylation, grafting ligands on the surface of nanocarriers; however, the nanocarriers need to be functionalized to release the drugs under stimulation at target sites. These modifications result in increased production steps which in turn lead to a higher final cost of the product. The cost-benefit balance should be beneficial for any product launched to be competitive on the market.” Hence it would be said that these novel techniques of smart drugs delivery systems have played a more important role in cancer treatment and it obvious they have more challenges day by day.

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